

Covalent organic polymer for CO₂ capture

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The climate change caused by carbon dioxide is an indispensable adjunct to the means of industrial development. This being so, substantial scientists from all over the world are focused on capture & sequestration of CO₂. Hence, lots of materials already prepared as a solution for CO₂ problems. Especially, liquid absorbent MEA (Monoethylamine) which contain amide functional group is most commonly used for CO₂ capture in these days. However, flue gas is heterogeneous and temperature is up to 40°C. This occur the corrosion and thermal degradation of MEA to be loss, decrease the efficiency of capturing the gas (8-35%) and, unable recycle by chemically irreversible change. Therefore in this research we design the materials which keep the benefit of the MEA, CO₂ capturing capacity, and improve their drawbacks.

Figure 1. Porous solid adsorbent, covalent organic polymer, capture the CO₂ selectively from flue gas and recycle easily.

To present new sorbent, we need to consider about several things. Affinity to capture the carbon dioxide (Zulfiqar et al., 2011), possible to selectively pull the target gas (Patel et al., 2013) and, suitable cost and be a green chemistry. Here, we synthesize solid adsorbent covalent organic polymer (COP) which inspired from adsorbing mechanism of tree and lung in human body. This solid adsorbent captured 59mg/g of CO₂ at 1bar and is comparable with MEA (60mg/g of CO₂). Also, without expensive or harmful catalyst it can be synthesized simply by organic compound. Heat of adsorption shows 26 kJ/mol which means this COP is easy to regenerate and recycle for CO₂ capture. Additionally, COP shows high selectivity, captured 61 times of CO₂ than N₂, and thermal stability up to 450°C.

From this research, we show that new idea of CO₂ adsorbent, COP, can alter conventional adsorbent by bio-mimic green chemistry. Furthermore, capturing capacity and stability can be improved more with tethering on the solid wall or impregnating metal ion or amine in the pore of structure.

- Patel, H. A., Je, S. H., Park, J., Chen, D. P., Jung, Y., Yavuz, C. T., & Coskun, A. (2013). Unprecedented high-temperature CO₂ selectivity in N₂-phobic nanoporous covalent organic polymers. *Nat Commun*, 4, 1357. doi: 10.1038/ncomms2359
- Zulfiqar, S., Karadas, F., Park, J., Deniz, E., Stucky, G. D., Jung, Y., . . . Yavuz, C. T. (2011). Amidoximes: promising candidates for CO₂ capture. *Energy & Environmental Science*, 4(11), 4528. doi: 10.1039/c1ee02264d